

Factors of Faculty Job Satisfaction in the Tertiary Travel Education: A Global Pandemic Scenario

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Abstract:

During this global pandemic, people in different sectors are really passing hectic days with mental and physical illness especially teachers or faculties who are providing online education at the tertiary level. This paper aims at finding the factors associated with job satisfaction for them. We discussed the job satisfaction attributes by using a regression model with factors analysis. For doing this research, we collected data from private and public universities in Bangladesh through Google form and analyzed the data with SPSS 26.0. The factors that we found through literature review include Monetary factors, Professional development factors, Physical factors, and psychological factors. We found that these factors have

a direct impact on job satisfaction for teachers at tertiary level especially in this global pandemic and found our model significant. This paper will be helpful for the university authority to take proper steps to enhance the job satisfaction for faculties.

Keywords: *job satisfaction, tertiary level education, Bangladesh, Covid-19, pandemic.*

Introduction

Virtual work or working from home was not predominantly an option for all industries before COVID-19, but somehow now it has become a new normal and unprecedented. It has always been an area of exploration, whether there is an association between working from home and employee job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a relative psychological feeling and understanding of an individual, which could change over the period of time based on different influencing or contributing factors like physical, financial, technological, social, and psychological. In this study, we have tried to explore how these factors are shaping employee job satisfaction and how a

supervised classification algorithm could be used to predict an employee as satisfied nor not. According to Manoj (2020), the idea of job satisfaction is difficult; nonetheless, adopting the correct variables and mechanisms can go a long way in improving employee performance. Working remotely, on the other hand, is more likely to become a common trend for some firms even after the epidemic, due to infrastructure investments, reduced paid travel costs, worker flexibility habits, and the desire to cut office space and daily utility costs. Furthermore, these costs can be efficiently passed on to employees, but this would be unjust to home workers (Pennington & Stanford, 2020).

Literature Review

Masum (2015) found that compensation packages, job security and working conditions. (Bodrud-Doza et al., 2020) stated that mental health status based on trauma for infectious of COVID19, losing relatives or own life, long time detachment of all the citizens, reduce satisfaction at home and workplace where job satisfaction of full-time professors in all levels of education is higher than other professions (Hesli & Lee, 2013). On the other hand, the achievement and recognition factors are very crucial to academics' job satisfaction; the two factors may overturn the influence of other factors (Hagedorn, 2002). A study conducted by (Bentley et al., 2013) found that 28% (n=1097) of the Australian universities' academics believed that their current profession is a source of personal strain where in Canada, 64% of the selected universities academics believed that the administrative process at the university level has been cumbersome. (Weinrib et al., 2013) and 42% of the university academics believed that their current profession creates personal strain (Weinrib et al., 2013). Along with different job satisfaction factors there are other three factors have been significantly important like, training and development opportunities, organizational culture and policy, and job security. Now these factors seem absent in this global pandemic and faculties are more insecure than others (Masum et al., 2015).

A well-structured academic process strongly affects the variations in the job satisfaction (Islam & Bari, 2019). The process has been collapsing due to the pandemic (Bentley et al., 2013). Full-time academics are enjoying a greater amount of satisfaction than part-time academics; the reasons are the full-time academics are receiving full support from their home institutions than the part-time academics. (Weinrib et al., 2013). Based on complexity and autonomy, job satisfaction has been highly correlated with the job performance (Judge et al., 2001). Personal influence, management from the institutions, involvement and support in academic works and infrastructural facilities are key to the job satisfaction. The above factors are in vulnerable state due to the existing global

pandemic (Bentley et al., 2013; Judge et al., 2001). Working conditions in higher education are deteriorating in South Africa, whereas the conditions might undoubtedly in critical stage during this pandemic (Wolhuter, 2013). The absence of most of the above is havoc during this global pandemic (Bentley et al., 2014).

Cabezas et. al. (2017) said that job satisfaction of a teacher has significant direct relationship with teacher's retention and commitment and performance. Employees in any organization require work flexibility. If a worker feels flexible, he or she will perform the task willingly and with interest. Working long hours is theoretically linked to lower productivity, health issues, and low employee motivation, all of which led to lower job satisfaction. A group of researchers (Pouwels et al., 2008) found that working hours were inversely connected to happiness using data from the German Socio-economic Panel Study (SOEP). Similarly, job happiness is influenced by the physical work environment. Although there are many studies connected to the work environment that pay little attention to the aspects of the physical work environment, evidence is mounting that the physical work environment has an impact on both job performance and job satisfaction (Vischer, 2007). For some people, the income they receive from their job reflects the amount of effort they put in. It means that, even though pamenty has a lot of net extrinsic effects, it is an intrinsic component (Rezaei et al., 2013). On the other side, if staff are not engaged in fostering teamwork, production may suffer, and job satisfaction may suffer as a result. Employees who are engaged perform better, are more committed, and loyal than those who are disengaged (Bakker, N/D). Sometimes other influencing factors may compensate dissatisfaction like, research, training and community services, those are playing significant role in the twenty-first century. Due to global pandemic the satisfaction through the same has been challenging (Arimoto & Daizen, 2013). Different physical supports to the academics are also important; research support, research funding, research equipment and libraries are significant in number for Polytechnic

institutions than Universities. The supports are questionable in this global pandemic (Arrevaara & Dobson, 2013).

Linear, U, and J shaped connections, as well as no significant relationships, have been documented in various investigations (Bernal et al., 1998). The relationship is still unresolved as a result of these contradictory findings, and the topic needs to be investigated further (Messenger et al., 2017).

Their findings support the manager's recommendation to leverage the factors that influence job performance to make an employee happy, improve their wellbeing, and improve the work environment (Dugguh & Ayaga, 2014). Another finding revealed that the majority of the academics postulated that their current profession is a great source of their personal strain. That seems even greater during this global pandemic (Balbachevsky & Schwartzman, 2013).

Methodology

This is a survey-based study, and the researchers collected responses from 77 academics working at public and private institutions of higher education. Our intended respondents were those academicians who provided their approval to participate in this survey, thus we employed the technique of convenience sampling to collect their responses. For data collection, a standardized questionnaire regarding work environment during a pandemic and overall job satisfaction was devised. Finally, we received just 77 respondents who carefully filled all the needed information. As a result, we have

included these respondents for data analysis. The questionnaire was constructed based on a five-point Likert scale, and the scale was disseminated appropriately. Calculations, a factor analysis, a reliability test, and multiple regressions were carried out with SPSS 26.0, and the results made it abundantly evident that the working environment has a significant bearing on job satisfaction. The Kaiser KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity and Cronbach's Alpha were applied to verify the reliability of the variables that were researched while using the SPSS Software. This was done to determine whether the sample was adequate. On the other hand, a Multiple Regression test was used to determine the impact of the work environment in the pandemic on job satisfaction from the point of view of academicians teaching in higher education systems. The appropriateness of factor analysis is examined by the KMO, which measures the sampling adequacy. On the other hand, the KMO measures sampling adequacy.

Results

The total number of respondents who filled out the survey was 77, and they came from a wide variety of academicians working in a variety of public and private educational institutions divided into 8 categories. First, demographic analyses were performed so that we could have a better knowledge of our sample. Table 1 provides a detailed presentation of the findings of an in-depth examination into demographic factors, including gender, teaching area, and institution, among others.

Table 1. Demographic Variables

Demographic Variables	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	60	77.9
	Female	17	22.1
Designation	Distinguished Professor	1	1.3
	Professor	16	20.8
	Associate Professor	11	14.3
	Assistant Professor	30	39.0
	Senior Lecturer	7	9.1
	Lecturer	11	14.3

	Lecturer(Entry-level)	1	1.3
Core teaching area	Social Science (Business studies, Economics etc.)	42	54.5
	Liberal Arts and Fine Arts	4	5.2
	Science	25	32.5
	Others	6	7.8
Type of teaching institution	Public	37	48.1
	Private	40	51.9
Institution Location	Barisal	1	1.3
	Chittagong	4	5.2
	Dhaka	49	63.6
	Khulna	4	5.2
	Rajshahi	7	9.1
	Rangpur	1	1.3
	Mymensingh	6	7.8
	Sylhet	5	6.5

Our sample consists of 77.90 percent male respondents and 22.10 percent female respondents, which indicates that our sample is representative of the population. In terms of the distribution of the sample's various designations, the designation of assistant professor has the highest proportion of respondents at 39 percent, while the designation of professor accounts for 20.80 percent, and the designations of associate professor and lecturer each make up 14.30 percent. The majority of respondents come from a social science background (business studies, economics, etc.), which accounts for 54.50 percent of the total. Respondents from a science background account for 32.5 percent of the total. We discovered a very low response rate from fine arts and liberal arts faculty (5.20 percent). Faculty members from public universities make up 48.10% of the respondents, while the remaining respondents are from private universities. The percentage of people who responded from the Dhaka division is 63.60 percent.

Cronbach's Alpha was the tool that was utilized in the "Reliability Test" to determine whether or not the study could be trusted. The SPSS software was utilized in the administration of the test. The following is a full explanation of the reliability tests that were performed on the measures of the variable that was studied:

Table 2. Reliability Statistics

SL. No	Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
1	Monetary	0.888	5
2	Professional Development	0.812	5
3	Physical facilities	0.731	5
4	Psychological factors	0.771	5
5	Job Satisfaction	0.670	

It is reliable for data collection because the cronbach Alpha value of the monetary variable factor is 0.888, the value of the professional development factor is.812, the value of the physical facilities factor is.731, the value of the psychological factor is.771, and the value of the job satisfaction factor is 0.670.

EFA Analysis of the Factors When one has obtained calculations on several variables and wants to identify the number and nature of underlying factors, "Exploratory Factor Analysis" was used to calculate the underlying factor structure of a set of data or a construct. This was done using the term "Exploratory Factor Analysis."

It is helpful to observe the interrelationships among the items of a scale that are used to reveal

the clusters of items that have enough common variation to justify their grouping together as a factor. These interrelationships are used to reveal the clusters of items that have enough common variation to justify their grouping together as a factor. Using this method, a collection of items is reduced to a more

manageable set of composite factors, with only a minimal amount of information being lost in the process. The Varimax Rotation with KMO and Bartlett's Test was applied to determine whether the sampling was adequate for all of the variables that were studied.

Table 3. KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

SL. No	Variables	KMO	Chi Square	Sig.
1	Monetary	0.808	235.479	0.000
2	Professional Development	0.767	137.911	0.000
3	Physical Facility	0.751	73.139	0.000
4	Psychological Factor	0.770	123.819	0.000
5	Job Satisfaction	0.804	865.391	0.000

The KMO is a tool that measures how adequately samples are taken, and it is used to evaluate whether factor analysis is appropriate. If the value is high (between 0.5 and 1.0), then factor analysis is the proper method to use. Since the independent variables in this study have KMO values of .808, .767, and .751, while the dependent variable has a KMO value of .804, factor analysis is an extremely suitable method for analyzing the data presented here. Bartlett's

sphericity test is utilized so that it can be ensured that the hypotheses about the variables are not invalidated inside the population. It has been evaluated using a Chi square, and the fact that its value has been found to be significant at a threshold of significance of 0.000 percent demonstrates that the data has a low sphericity and is therefore appropriate for factor analysis. The following is a list of various information regarding factors:

Table 4. Factors Analysis (Independent Variables)

Sl.No.	Factor Name	Eigen Value	% of Variance Explained	Item Converged	Item Loading
1	Monetary	7.124	33.924	1. I am happy with the promotional opportunities which still exist during COVID 19.	0.685
				2. I am happy as there is no negative impact on my salary during the global pandemic.	0.887
				3. I am happy as I am getting all the compensation-benefits in this COVID 19 situation.	0.992
				4. I am happy as I am getting payment for extra work load during pandemic.	0.818
				5. I am happy with the availability of research grants in my insulations at this COVID 19 period.	0.835
2	Professional Development	3.288	15.658	1. I am happy as I am getting ample professional opportunities to improve myself after pandemic starts.	0.771
				2. I am happy as my institution is very keen to invest in developing teaching-learning competencies of the faculties.	0.862
				3. I am happy as I am learning different new "Learning Management Systems (LMS)" to equip with new sorts of technology and systems.	0.689
				4. I am happy as my teaching performance is better than prior to the COVID 19.	0.574

				5. I am happy with the research opportunities offered by my institutions.	0.860
3	Physical Facility	1.331	6.34	1. Lack of face to face communication hinders the proper transformation of knowledge.	0.762
				2. Lack of physical teaching tools; such as physical white boards, markers etc. suffers me.	0.731
				3. Lack of physical movement during online lectures creates physical hardship like ergonomics problems.	0.714
				4. At present, all the administrative processes are not easily available.	0.608
				5. I can't use the office space that is useful for teaching.	0.656
4	Psychological Factor	1.239	5.90	1. I think job retention has been very challenging in this pandemic.	0.536
				2. I think work commitment has been deteriorating during COVID 19.	0.577
				3. I think recognition of works is not perfectly supervised.	0.549
				4. I think more variety of tasks actually decreases my work efficiency.	0.809
				5. I think working extra hours due to online education creates mental stress.	0.771
				6. I think there is an imbalance between work and life.	0.803

"Factor Analysis of Job Satisfaction": The analysis of factors led to the identification of a single factor. Table 5 contains information regarding the factors, including factor names and variable numbers, as well as variable convergence and their eigen values. The value of 0.368 for the R squared statistic provides insight

into the nature of the connection that exists between the independent variables (IV) and the dependent variable (DV). The R, R squared, and R squared adjusted for the model are displayed in the regression table, along with the estimate's standard error.

Table 5. Factors Analysis (Dependent Variables)

Sl.No.	Factor Name	Eigen Value	% of Variance Explained	Factor Loading
1	Job Satisfaction	4.391	43.908	0.688

According to the results presented in the table, the independent factors significantly accounted for 36.68 percentage points of the total variation in the dependent variable known as job satisfaction. As indicated in Exhibit F, the model that is well adjusted is the one that considers monetary factor, physical facilities, professional development, psychological factors, and job satisfaction. The F statistic is calculated by dividing the square half residual by the square half of the square half. In addition, an ANOVA table was used to test the quality of fit for the model. At a significance level of 1 percent, the model was found to have a significant F value of 8.373, which indicates that the model is a good

fit for the data. Since the t-value is significant at the 5% level of significance, the result of the coefficient indicates that independent variables have direct effect on job satisfaction. This can be deduced from the fact that the level of significance was set at 5%. The coefficient presents the values of the coefficients for every model that was examined. Take note that all of the models have a p-value that is lower than 0.05, meaning that they are statistically significant (p). Except for supervisor role and growth Opportunities, the importance of this predictor variable does have a contribution in the outcome variable. The feelings that are associated with certain aspects of one's job are what constitute

job satisfaction. As a result, the alternative hypothesis states that there is a positive relationship between IV and DV, indicating that there is a significant effect of work environment

on job satisfaction in the respective constructs, which are the fundamental components that make up work environment.

Table 6. Variables Matrix

Dependent Variables (Job Satisfaction)			
Independent Variables	Beta Value	t-Statistics	P-Value
Monetary	0.271	8.821	0.000
Professional Development	0.215	4.268	0.001
Physical Facility	0.207	3.449	0.002
Psychological Factor	0.206	3.314	0.000
R	0.591		
R-Square	0.368		
Adjusted R Square	0.313		
F-Value	8.373		
Durbin-Watson Statistics	1.869		

Discussion

The outcome of this research will be helpful for the future research endeavors. We have done the research based on university faculties only, but other researchers may use this paper for the employee’s job satisfaction of other sectors like telecommunication, IT companies etc. On the overhand, the factors which we have identified through this research may be useful in case of enhancing job satisfaction. The faculties, both in private and public universities of Bangladesh, have been transforming themselves to a new learning and teaching management systems due to this global pandemic. They bound to adopt the new system, sometimes due to their own fascination of teaching or due to their teaching profession as bread and butter. By the sake of never ending process of education and responsibilities, faculties sacrificed their satisfaction level that we have identified in this well-timed research article. The faculty job satisfaction level in the lower and the middle level is even worse than the tertiary level that we explored. Many schools, colleges and kindergartens in the lower and middle level of education in Bangladesh have shut down due to fund crises in the global pandemic. There are always chains of job satisfaction from lower to

tertiary level of education. The higher the job satisfaction in the lower and middle level of education generates better transformation of knowledge and job satisfaction in the tertiary level. These chains have been collapsed due to this pandemic, though these chains have been trying to revive after the pandemic. Government of Bangladesh has taken different expansionary fiscal policies through transfer payments but those were inadequate. This article will be the mirror image of job satisfaction level of many faculties in the tertiary level. The conventional factors of faculty job satisfaction along with our explored few factors need to be addressed and to be resolved with high priority.

Conclusion

Job satisfaction is not a new issue, but it varies depending on the context and the level employee types as well as nature of the business. Working from home has the potential to result in increased work intensity due to the desire to work long hours and the overlap of paid and personal lives. Home-based teleworkers, for example, report better work-life balance, but "high mobility" workers are more at risk of poor health and wellbeing. The relevant factors in

most research works for job satisfaction in academic institutions are job security, career growth, remuneration, relations with co-workers, workload, relations with top management, environment in the workplace and opportunities of financing in research.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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